

NanoCommons

Nano-Knowledge Community

The European Nanotechnology Community Informatics Platform: Bridging data and disciplinary gaps for industry and regulators

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10th General Assembly – M54
GoToMeeting/Limassol, 15th – 27th June 2022

NUID UCD role in NanoCommons

- JRA:** UCD led two **JRA3 (WP5 Analysis and modelling tools)** and contributed to all other JRA activities. UCD provided new multiscale modelling tools and data, and contributed to the development of integrated workflows and ontologies
- NA:** UCD participated in NA
- TA:** UCD completed **1 TA project (3 TA projects in progress)**

NUID UCD objectives in NanoCommons

- Purchase and installation of a DELL computational server at the Daedalus Data Center of UCD for parallel computing, i.e, MPI and GPU for performing high-throughput calculations
- Computational platform created for developed tools and open source software (Deliverable 5.3)
- All software is efficiently implemented. Python scripts are used for the evaluation of computational data
- MODA for intrinsic and extrinsic descriptors following EMMC rules and application tools
- Basic intrinsic descriptors as band gaps and extrinsic descriptors as immersion enthalpies in water and organic solvents ($\log P$): database for many metals, metal oxides and carbon based materials of interest in comparison to literature data if available
- For immersion enthalpies comparison with Hamaker constants and surface energies

Open source software for the evaluation of theoretical descriptors

Computational tool	Implementation	Methodology
MOPAC	GPU	HF (semi-empirical)
SIESTA	MPI	DFT
GROMACS	MPI, GPU	MD
GFN-xTB	MKL, OpenMP	TB-DFT and MD
LAMMPS	MPI	MD
CP2K	MPI	BOMD, DFT

PowerEdge C4140 Server (DELL) system with 4 GPU (NVIDIA Tesla V100 SXM2 32GB GPU Accelerator for NVLink) and 2 CPU (Intel Xeon Platinum 8160 2.1GHz, 24C/48T, 10.4GT/s, 33M Cache, Turbo, HT-150W DDR4-2666).

2 workstations with NVIDIA Quadro RTX 5000

PCCP Hot paper 2021: intrinsic and extrinsic and bionano interface descriptors

Multiscale model: Corona tool

- Corona tool provides through a multiscale model (UA) heat maps, i.e. minima of Boltzmann averaged orientations of pre-optimized protein structures on nanomaterials
- **Input:** PMFs, zeta potentials and Hamaker constants
- **Output:** Heat maps, i.e. adsorption energies of proteins on nanomaterials for a range of NM sizes and surface charges
- Implementation of corona tool in KB by BIOMAX (Deliverable 5.6)
- MODA for corona modelling through UA with the EMMC app

Immersion enthalpies

$$\log P (\text{org. solv./water}) = \log \{C_{\text{NP}}(\text{org. solv.})/C_{\text{NP}}(\text{water})\}$$

Chemisorption and physisorption studies of single water (or hydroxyl) molecules where entropic contribution to free energy in different temperatures is included, solvation energies and surface energies may aid in the interpretation of logP values, i.e. relative hydrophilicity or hydrophobicity as well as contact angle calculations

Wulff NM 2nm radius	Immersion enthalpies in water (LAMMPS)
Metals	NVT MD simulations, (KJ/mol) nm⁻²
Ag	-1380.149327
Au	-1383.993085
Cu	-1150.394307
Ni	-1420.30323
Al	-1379.158268
Pb	-1310.843722
Pt	-1338.292344
Pd	-1277.798048
Ni > Au > Ag > Al > Pt > Pb > Pd > Cu	

- Band gap
- Polarizability
- Ionization potential
- Electron affinity
- Hamaker constant
- Immersion enthalpy
- Potential of mean force (PMF)
- Adsorption energy of a protein on a nanoparticle

MOPAC
MOPAC
xTB
xTB
Hamaker constant
tool
GROMACS
GROMACS
United Atom tool
(UA)

EMMC templates and OSMO ontology

- Demonstration case and TA and publication with PLUS:

Simulation tools for transport and corona formation

Tools for characterisation of the bionano interface, which are required for prediction of MIE/KE, were further improved and automated. We are using the SmartNanoTox multiscale modelling methodology, which has been developed to build coarse-grained (CG) models of lipid membranes and proteins and predict their interaction with nanoparticles. The calculation of bionano interactions includes four stages, which was integrated into a single prediction tool.

Role of allergens with known properties as part of the corona

The predicted ranking and corona content was validated by direct simulation of competitive adsorption of proteins on NM and attachment to a lipid bilayer

- AOP service and publication:

Developed prediction tools for adverse outcome and toxicity pathways (AOP/TP) based on the likelihood of the molecular initiating events (MIE) and KeyEvents (KE). Catalogue evidence relating to relevant AOP/TP to allow identification of candidate MIE/KE events at bionano interface. Examples of such MIE/KE are: NM cell association and uptake, adsorption of NM at lipid membrane, binding a ligand in a given biological fluid, NM unfolding adsorbed proteins, production of reactive oxygen species, dissolution and ion release, etc.

First MIE prediction tool has been implemented and made available via web interface

- *Predictive toxicity assessment of semiconductor quantum dots that are used as fluorescence probes – adverse effects on the human lung epithelial carcinoma cell line A549 (“QD-cytotox”) Dr. Florian Part et al. (BOKU) and Dr. Jean-Pascal Piret et al. (UNAMUR)*

Modelling with Nanohub tools - Basic descriptors with semi-empirical xTB and MOPAC software and Nanohub PMFs of coatings on QDs (PEG and DHLA) is still needed to be calculated to retrieve adsorption energies and share data for statistical modelling with NovaMechanics

- *In silico characterisation and a QSAR model for in vivo lung inflammation for a set of 50 Smart NanoTox materials*
Application by Dr Ottmar Schmid (Helmholtz-Zentrum Muenchen) to be submitted

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Thank you

Any Questions?

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